

 H_φ FAZOSI VA UNING KLASSIFIKATSIYASI<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7843803>**O'razaliyev shirinboy bo'ron o'g'li***samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis instituti, shirinboy.urazaliyev@mail.ru*

Annotatsiya: $f(x)$ funksiyaning $[a, b]$ dagi modul uzluksizligi, H_φ fazosi va uning xarakteristikasi.

Аннотация: Непрерывность по модулю функции $f(x)$ в $[a, b]$, пространстве H_φ ее характеристика.

Annotation: Modulo continuity of function $f(x)$ in $[a, b]$, space H_φ and its characteristic.

1-ta'rif. $\omega(\delta) \in \Phi$ bo'lsin. Agar $[a, b]$ da aniqlangan uzluksiz funksiya quyidagi

$$\sup_{0 < \delta \leq b-a} \frac{\omega(f, \delta)}{\omega(\delta)} = H_\omega(f) < \infty$$

Shartini qanoatlantirsa (Bunda $\omega(f, \delta) - f(x)$ funksiyaning $[a, b]$ dagi modul uzluksizligi), u holda $f \in H_\omega(f)$ deyiladi. Bundan keyin qisqacha $H_\omega(f)$ ning o'rniga H_ω deb ishlatib ketayveramiz.

$\omega(\delta)$ – funksiya H_ω sinfnig xarakteristikasi deyiladi.

2-ta'rif. $\omega(\delta) \in \Phi$ bo'lsin. Agar $\exists C_f > 0$ bo'lib, $\omega(f, \delta) \leq C_f \omega(\delta)$ tengsizlik bajarilsa, u holda $f \in H_\omega$ deyiladi.

1-lemma. H_ω – to'plam, kompleks sonlar maydonida chiziqli sistemani tashkil etadi.

Isbot. Lemmani isbot qilish uchun

1). $\forall f, g \in H_\omega \Rightarrow f + g \in H_\omega$,

2). $\forall \lambda \in (\mathbb{Z}), f \in H_\omega \Rightarrow \lambda f \in H_\omega$

ekanligini ko'rsatish yetarli.

$f, g \in H_\omega$ bo'lsin $\Rightarrow \exists C_f, C_g > 0, \forall \delta \in (0, l_0]$ uchun

$$\omega(f, \delta) \leq C_f \omega(\delta), \quad \omega(g, \delta) \leq C_g \omega(\delta)$$

bu tengsizliklardan

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(f + g, \delta) &\leq \omega(f, \delta) + \omega(g, \delta) \leq C_f \omega(\delta) + C_g \omega(\delta) = (C_f + C_g) \omega(\delta) \Rightarrow \\ &\Rightarrow f + g \in H_\omega \end{aligned}$$

$$\omega(\lambda f, \delta) \leq |\lambda| \omega(f, \delta) \leq |\lambda| C_f \omega(\delta) \Rightarrow \lambda f \in H_\omega.$$

2-lemma. H_ω – cheksiz o'lchovli chiziqli sistema.

3-lemma. $H_\omega \in C(\Gamma)$.

$C(\Gamma)$ – Γ da uzluksiz bo'lgan funksiyalar sinfi

1-teorema. H_ω fazosi (1) norma bo'lishicha Banax fazosi bo'ladi.

3-ta'rif. B_1 va B_2 lar Banax fazosi bo'lib, $B_1 \subseteq B_2$ bo'lsin. B_1 ning B_2 da yotishi to'la uzluksiz deyildi, agarda $\|f_n - f_0\|_{B_1} \rightarrow 0 \Rightarrow \|f_n - f_0\|_{B_2} \rightarrow 0$, $f_n, f_0 \in B_1$ bo'lsa.

4-lemma. B_1 va B_2 fazolar Banax fazosi bo'lib, $B_1 \subseteq B_2$ yotishi to'la uzluksiz bo'lsin, agar B_1 cheksiz o'lchovli bo'lsa, u holda $B_1 \subset B_2$ (B_1, B_2 – ning to'g'ri qismi bo'ladi)

4-ta'rif. B_1 va B_2 fazolar- Banax fazosi bo'lib, $B_1 \subseteq B_2$ bo'lsin. Agar B_1 ning ixtiyoriy chegaralangan qismi B_2 da kompakt bo'lsa, u holda B_1 ning B_2 da yotishi kompakt deyildi.

5-ta'rif. Uzluksiz va kompakt vlojeniya (yotishi) to'la uzluksiz deb ataladi.

uzluksiz va kompakt bo'lsa, ya'ni u B_1 ning ixtiyoriy chegaralangan to'plamini B_2 ning kompakt qismiga ko'chirsa, u holda A operator to'la uzluksiz operator deyiladi.

5-lemma. $\varphi \in \Phi$ bo'lsin. H_φ fazo, C_Γ da to'la uzluksiz bo'ladi.

2-teorema. $\varphi \in \Phi$ bo'lsa H_φ fazo C_Γ ning to'g'ri qismi bo'ladi.

Isbot. Bu teoremaning isboti H_φ fazoning cheksiz o'lchovliligidan, H_φ ning C_Γ da yotishining (vlosheniya) to'la uzluksizligi va yuqoridagi 3-lemmadan kelib chiqadi.

6-lemma. $\varphi_1, \varphi_2 \in \Phi$ va $\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \frac{\varphi_1(\delta)}{\varphi_2(\delta)} = 0$ bo'lsa, u holda $H_{\varphi_1} \subset H_{\varphi_2}$ va vlosheniya (H_{φ_1} ning H_{φ_2} da yotishi) to'la uzluksiz bo'ladi.

3-teorema. $\varphi_1, \varphi_2 \in \Phi$ bo'lsin. Agar: 1) $\varphi_1(\delta) \sim \varphi_2(\delta)$ bo'lsa, u holda $H_{\varphi_1} = H_{\varphi_2}$ bo'ladi.

2) $\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \frac{\varphi_1(\delta)}{\varphi_2(\delta)} = 0$ bo'lsa, u holda $H_{\varphi_1}, H_{\varphi_2}$ ning to'g'ri qismi bo'ladi.

Isbot. [$\varphi_1(\delta), \varphi_2(\delta) > 0$, $\varphi_1(\delta) \sim \varphi_2(\delta)$ deyildi agarda $\exists A_1, A_2 > 0, \forall \delta$ uchun $A_1 \varphi_2(\delta) \leq \varphi_1(\delta) \leq A_2 \varphi_2(\delta)$ bo'lsa]

Bu ta'rifga asosan teorema birinchi qismining isboti birdaniga kelib chiqadi :

$H_{\varphi_1} \subseteq H_{\varphi_2}$ ekanligini ko'rsatamiz.

Agar $\varphi_1 \leq m \varphi_2$ bo'lsa $\Rightarrow \|f\|_{\varphi_2} \leq m \|f\|_{\varphi_1}$.

$\varphi_2 \leq n \varphi_1$ bo'lsa $H_{\varphi_2} \subseteq H_{\varphi_1}$ va $\|f\|_{H_{\varphi_1}} \leq n \|f\|_{H_{\varphi_2}}$

teoremaning ikkinchi qismini H_{φ_1} ning H_{φ_2} da etishi to'la uzluksizligi va ularning cheksiz o'lchovida, hamda 2-3 lemmalardan kelib chiqadi.

H_φ da normani quyidagicha kiritamiz:

$$\|f\|_{H_\varphi} = \max_{t \in \gamma} |f(t)| + \sup_{0 < \delta \leq l} \frac{\omega(f, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)}, \quad \varphi \in \Phi_{[0, a]} \quad (1)$$

4-teorema. (1) norma bo'yicha H_φ fazosi to'la bo'ladi.

Isbot. $\forall \{f_n\} \in H_\varphi$, $\{f_n\}$ – fundamental ketma-ketlik bo'lsin $\Rightarrow$

$$\forall \varepsilon > 0, \exists N, m, n > N \text{ boshlab } \|f_m - f_n\|_{H_\varphi} < \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

tengsizlik o'rinli bo'ladi. (2) ni (1) ni e'tiborga olganda

$$\|f_m - f_n\|_{H_\varphi} = \max_{t \in \gamma} |f_m - f_n| + \sup_{0 < \delta \leq l} \frac{\omega(f_m - f_n, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} < \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

(3) dan $\{f_n\}$ ketma-ketlik $C(\gamma)$ da ham fundamental bo'ladi

$$\|f_m - f_n\|_{C_T} < \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

Ma'lumki, $C(\gamma)$ – to'liq fazo. Shuning uchun $\exists f_0 \in C(\gamma)$

$$\|f_m - f_n\|_{C_T} \rightarrow_{n \rightarrow \infty} 0 \quad (5)$$

Endi $f_0 \in H_\varphi$ ekanligini ko'rsatamiz.

Ma'lumki, fundamental ketma-ketlik chegaralangan ketma-ketlik bo'ladi

$$\exists r > 0, \forall n \text{ uchun } \|f_n\|_{H_\varphi} \leq r \Rightarrow \frac{\omega(f_n, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} \leq r, \forall n, \delta \Rightarrow \omega(f_n, \delta) \leq r\varphi(\delta).$$

$$[\omega(f - g, \delta) \geq |\omega(f, \delta) - \omega(g, \delta)|, \quad \omega(f + g, \delta) \geq |\omega(f, \delta) + \omega(g, \delta)|$$

$$\omega(f, \delta) = \omega(f - g + g, \delta) \leq \omega(f - g, \delta) + \omega(g, \delta) \Rightarrow$$

$$\omega(f, \delta) - \omega(g, \delta) \leq \omega(f - g, \delta)$$

$$\omega(g, \delta) - \omega(f, \delta) \leq \omega(g - f, \delta) \quad \text{xuddi shunday}$$

$$|\omega(f, \delta) - \omega(g, \delta)| \leq \omega(f - g, \delta)$$

Agar $f_n \rightrightarrows f_0$ bo'lsa $\omega(f, \delta) \rightrightarrows \omega(f_0, \delta)$ bo'ladi. $f_n \rightrightarrows f_0$ bo'lsin, $\forall \delta$

$$\omega(f_0, \delta) \leq r\varphi(\delta) \Rightarrow f_0 \in H_\varphi$$

Endi $\|f_n - f_0\|_{H_\varphi} \rightarrow_{n \rightarrow \infty} 0$ ekanligini ko'rsatamiz. $\|f_n - f_0\|_{C_T} \rightarrow_{n \rightarrow \infty} 0$ bo'lganligi

uchun $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \frac{\omega(f_n - f_0, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} = 0$ ekanligini ko'rsatish yetarli (2) dan $\forall \varepsilon > 0, \exists N, m, n >$

$$N \sup_{\delta} \frac{\omega(f_m - f_n, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} < \varepsilon \Rightarrow \sup_{\delta} \omega(f_m - f_n, \delta) < \varepsilon \varphi(\delta) \Rightarrow \text{Bundan}$$

$n > N$ ni belgilab $m \rightarrow \infty$ $\omega(f_m - f_n, \delta) < \varepsilon \varphi(\delta)$ da limitga o'tamiz:

$$\omega(f_0 - f_n, \delta) \leq \varepsilon \varphi(\delta) \Rightarrow \frac{\omega(f_0 - f_n, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} \leq \varepsilon \Rightarrow \sup_{\delta} \frac{\omega(f_0 - f_n, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} \leq \varepsilon \quad (5)$$

(4) bilan (5) dan H_φ ning to'liqligi kelib chiqadi.

7-lemma. Agar $\|U_n - U_0\|_{C_T} \rightarrow 0$ bo'lsa, $\|\omega(U_n, \delta) - \omega(U_0, \delta)\|_{C_T} \rightarrow 0$ bo'ladi.

5-teorema. H_φ fazo to'liq fazo.

Isbot. $\{f_n\}$ – fundamental ketma-ketlik $\{f_n\} \in H_\varphi$ bo'lsin. $\{f_n\} - C_T$ da fundamental. C_T – to'liq fazo bo'lganligi uchun $\exists f_0, f_0 \in C_T$, ya'ni

$$\|f_n - f_0\|_{C_T} \rightarrow 0 \quad (6)$$

$\{f_n\}$ ketma-ketlik H_φ da fundamental bo'lganligi uchun u chegaralangan bo'ladi, ya'ni $\forall n$ uchun $\|f_n\|_{H_\varphi} \leq r. \quad 0 < r < +\infty$

$$\|f_n\|_{H_\varphi} = \|f_n\|_{C_T} + \sup_{\delta} \frac{\omega(f_n, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} \leq r$$

bo'lgani uchun $\omega(f_n, \delta) \leq r\varphi(\delta)$ (1) va 1-lemmaga asosan

$$\omega(f_n, \delta) \leq r\varphi(\delta) \Rightarrow f_0 \in H_\varphi$$

Endi $\|f_n - f_0\|_{H_\varphi} \rightarrow 0$ bo'lishini ko'rsatamiz

$$\|f_n - f_0\|_{H_\varphi} = \|f_n - f_0\|_{C_T} + \sup_{\delta} \frac{\omega(f_n - f_0, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)}$$

(1) ga asosan $\|f_n - f_0\|_{C_T} \rightarrow 0$ va $\sup_{\delta} \frac{\omega(f_n - f_0, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} \rightarrow 0$ ko'rsatish yetarli $\{f_n\} \in H_{\varphi}$ da fundamental bo'lganligi uchun $\exists N$ nomer topiladiki $m, n > N$ uchun $\|f_n - f_m\|_{\varphi} < \varepsilon$ bo'ladi. Bundan $\sup \frac{\omega(f_n - f_0, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} < \varepsilon$, $\frac{\omega(f_n - f_0, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} < \varepsilon$,
 $\omega(f_n - f_0, \delta) < \varepsilon \varphi(\delta)$ bo'ladi $\Rightarrow \sup \frac{\omega(f_n - f_0, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} \leq \varepsilon \Rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\omega(f_n - f_0, \delta)}{\varphi(\delta)} \rightarrow 0$

Demak, H_{φ} fazo to'liq fazo ekan.

Agar $f \in H_{\varphi}$ bo'lsa, $\forall m > 0$ uchun $mf \in H_{\varphi}$ bo'ladi va $H_{\varphi} = H_{m\varphi}$ bo'ladi. Endi $\forall H_{\varphi_1}$ va H_{φ_2} sinflar qaysi vaqtda bir-biridan farq qiladi.

6-ta'rif. $B_1 \subseteq B_2$ to'la uzluksiz deyiladi: B_1 dagi har bir chegaralangan ketma-ketlik B_2 da kompakt bo'lsa va B_1 da yaqinlashuvchiligidan B_2 da yaqinlashuvchiligi kelib chiqsa.

Teorema (Riss). Har bir B fazo chekli o'lchovli bo'lishi uchun uning chegaralangan qismi kompakt bo'lishi zarur va yetarli.

Xulosa.

Ushbu maqola H_{φ} fazosi va uning xarakteristikasini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. В. А. Какичев. «Граничные свойства интеграла типа Коши многих переменных». Уч. зап. Шахт. пед. ин-та. 2, вып. 6, 1959-г, 25-90 с.
2. Ф. Д. Гахов. «Краевые задачи». Москва. Наука. 1977-г.
3. Н. И. Мусхелишвили. «Сингулярные интегральные уравнения». Москва. Наука. 1968-г.
4. Б. А. Фукс. «Теория аналитических функций многих комплексных переменных». М. Л. 1948-г.
5. А. G'oziyev. «Analitik funksiyaning chegaraviy masalalari va singulyar integral tenglamalar». Samarqand-2018.